

EU-LIFE CoARA Action Plan

Introduction

Research assessment is a priority for EU-LIFE. As such, since its creation, EU-LIFE has been working with its member institutes, policymakers and funders on **good practices that promote responsible research assessment**. This action plan outlines how EU-LIFE will continue to promote and support the reform of research assessment within the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

In its first part, this action plan includes the **past & current actions** that EU-LIFE has been taking since 2021 towards the design and implementation of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and CoARA.

In its second part, it focuses on the **longer-term actions** that EU-LIFE will carry out to further contribute to the reform of research assessment by studying, developing and promoting the use of assessment practices aligned with CoARA commitments in research institutes.

In particular:

At the institutional level

Revision of institutional indicators for benchmarking: Identify and promote the use of qualitative indicators and new, or an evolution of, metrics to complement the responsible use of quantitative indicators in the assessment of diverse scientific outputs from research institutes in EU-LIFE.

At the individual level

Revision of processes and criteria in research assessment: Collect information and develop recommendations aligned with CoARA principles and commitments on the institutional policies for recruitment and evaluation of researchers and professionals at the interface of science (e.g. Research managers and administrators, core facilities) in all career stages.

Past & current actions

1

Raise awareness about CoARA & the reform of research assessment

- 1.1 **Inform** internally in EU-LIFE about CoARA.
- 1.2 **Inform** internally in EU-LIFE about the advancements in the reform of research assessment.
- 1.3 **Provide internal opportunities** for EU-LIFE researchers to engage in research assessment discussion.
- 1.4 Act as **ambassadors for CoARA** and the reform of research assessment when possible.

2

Provide advice & feedback towards advancing in research assessment

- 2.1 **Provide feedback** to CoARA consultations.
- 2.2 Provide insights for **policy debates in the ERA** about research assessment.

3

Actively promote advancements in research assessment

- 3.1 Promote & **contribute to the discussion** towards the reform of the research assessment system (before creation of CoARA).
- 3.2 Participate in the **creation of CoARA**.
- 3.3 Participate actively in **CoARA WGs**.
- 3.4 Promote the **use of practices in research assessment** aligned with DORA and CoARA.
- 3.5 Promote **dialogue between the scientific community and policy makers** in research assessment.

Longer-term actions (2024-2028)

3 Actively promote advancements in research assessment

3.6 Institutional level: Identify and promote the use of qualitative indicators and new, or an evolution of, metrics to complement the responsible use of quantitative indicators in the assessment of diverse scientific outputs from our research institutes.

3.7 Individual level (researchers): Collect information and develop recommendations aligned with CoARA principles and commitments on the institutional policies for recruitment and career evaluation of researchers in all career stages.

3.8 Individual level (core facilities staff): Collect information and develop recommendations aligned with CoARA principles and commitments on the institutional policies for recruitment and career evaluation of core facilities personnel in all career stages.

3.9 Individual level (research managers and administrators): Collect information and develop recommendations aligned with CoARA principles and commitments on the institutional policies for recruitment and career evaluation of research managers and administrators in all career stages.

April 2024

Marta Agostinho, EU-LIFE Executive Officer
Iris Uribealgo, EU-LIFE Policy Officer & CoARA Team Leader
EU-LIFE Policy Task Force
EU-LIFE Strategy Group

Layout: Esther Dorado-Ladera, EU-LIFE Communications Officer

For further information please contact the EU-LIFE Office: contact@eu-life.eu

To cite this work please use the following sentence:
EU-LIFE (2024). *EU-LIFE CoARA Action Plan*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843655>

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> or send a letter to Creative Commons, PO Box 1866, Mountain View, CA 94042, USA.

EU-LIFE Office
Room 429, Centre for Genomic Regulation
C/ Dr. Aiguader, 88, 08003 Barcelona, Spain
www.eu-life.eu
contact@eu-life.eu

www.eu-life.eu

contact@eu-life.eu

[/company/EU-LIFE](https://www.linkedin.com/company/EU-LIFE)

[@EULIFE_news](https://twitter.com/EULIFE_news)

EU-LIFE is an alliance of research centres whose mission is to support and strengthen European research excellence. EU-LIFE members are leading research institutes in their countries and internationally renowned for producing excellent research, widely transferring knowledge and nurturing talent.

EU-LIFE Partners

Center for Genomic Regulation (CRG, Spain) | Central European Institute of Technology (CEITEC, Czech Republic) | European Institute of Oncology (IEO, Italy) | Flanders Institute For Biotechnology (VIB, Belgium) | Friedrich Miescher Institute for Biomedical Research (FMI, Switzerland) | Institut Curie (France) | Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM, Finland) | Institute of Molecular Biology & Biotechnology (IMBB FORTH, Greece) | Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciência (IGC, Portugal) | International Institute of Molecular and Cell biology in Warsaw (IIMCB, Poland) | Max Delbrück Center for Molecular Medicine in the Helmholtz Association (MDC, Germany) | Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences (CeMM, Austria) | The Babraham Institute (Babraham, United Kingdom) | The Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI, The Netherlands) | The University of Copenhagen Biotech Research & Innovation Centre (BRIC, Denmark)

EU-LIFE